

STUDIES ON 3-*m*-TOLYL-2:4-THIAZOLIDIONE AND 5-ARYLAZO-3-PHENYL-2-PHENYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDONES

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3-*m*-Tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione has been condensed with aldehydes and its degradation products as well as characteristic reactions have been studied. Further, 5-arylazo-3-phenyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidones have been obtained by condensing 3-phenyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone with aryl diazonium chlorides.

In continuation to the earlier work on 3-aryl-2:4-thiazolidiones (Bhargava *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 463; 1956, **33**, 596), it was considered worthwhile to prepare 3-*m*-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione and 3-phenyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone.

The thiazolidione has been obtained by the interaction of *S*-di-*m*-tolylthiourea with monochloroacetic acid in glacial acetic acid and the thiazolidone prepared by the interaction of *S*-diphenylthiourea with monochloroacetic acid in absolute alcohol in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate. The reactive methylene group of the thiazolidione has been successfully condensed with six aromatic aldehydes and that of the thiazolidone with six aryl diazonium chlorides, yielding respectively 5-arylidene-2:4-thiazolidiones and 5-arylazo-substituted thiazolidones. The attachment of the azo group to -CH₂- group in position-5 in α -position to the activating carbonyl group is justified by the arguments advanced by Meerwein *et al.* (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, **152**, 237)* and is further supported by the observation that when the -CH₂- group in position-5 of the thiazolidone nucleus is blocked by condensation with aromatic aldehydes, no azo dye is formed.

Further, mercuration of 3-*m*-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione with mercuric acetate has yielded 3-acetoxymercuri-*m*-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione. The acetoxymercuri group is assumed to enter the aryl nucleus.

The thiazolidione on decomposition with KOH has yielded *m*-toluidine, as confirmed by the preparation of its azo- β -naphthol derivative, and on oxidation with KMnO₄ in glacial acetic acid, 3-*m*-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione-sulphone, as confirmed by analytical data.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-*m*-Tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione was prepared according to the method of Markley and Reid (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 2137) in glacial acetic acid in needles, m.p. 90°. (Found: S, 15.56. C₁₀H₉O₂NS requires S, 15.49%).

3-*m*-Tolyl-5-benzylidene-2:4-thiazolidione.—A mixture of thiazolidione (0.5 g.) and benzaldehyde (0.35 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (12 c.c.), and fused sodium acetate (1 g.) was heated under reflux for 1½ hours. On pouring the contents into water, a yellow precipitate was obtained. After keeping overnight, the yellow precipitate was filtered off and the product was crystallised from alcohol.

Similarly other aldehydes were condensed, yielding 5-arylidene derivatives. The properties and analytical data of these derivatives are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
3-*m*-Tolyl-5-arylidene-2:4-thiazolidione.

Aldehyde.	% Yield.	M.P.	Sulphur%	
			Found.	Calc.
Benzaldehyde	65	105°	10.80	10.84
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	60	201°	9.36	9.41
Vanillin	75	150°	9.32	9.30
Anisaldehyde	72	72°	9.80	9.84
Cinnamaldehyde	70	100°	9.89	9.96
Piperonal	69	116°	9.16	9.43

Decomposition of 3-m-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione.—The thiazolidione (1 g) was boiled with 40% KOH (50 c.c.) on a water-bath for 2 hours. The reaction mixture on distillation gave a liquid, which was confirmed as *m*-toluidine by the preparation of its azo- β -naphthol derivative, m.p. 140°.

3-Acetoxymercuri-m-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione.—The thiazolidione (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) and to this absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) and mercuric acetate (1.5 g.), dissolved in water (15 c.c.) and acidified with acetic acid, were added. After 24 hours, a precipitate was obtained, which was filtered, washed respectively with dilute acetic acid and hot water, and crystallised from alcohol in a pale yellow form, m.p. 265°. (Found: Hg, 42.7S. C₁₂H₁₁O₄NSHg requires Hg, 43.08%).

3-m-Tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione-sulphone.—3-*m*-Tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) and treated slowly with KMnO₄ (1 g.), dissolved in water (40 c.c.), at 0°. The precipitate, obtained after removing excess of KMnO₄ and chilling, was washed with ice-water, dried and crystallised from absolute alcohol in a yellow form, m.p. 116°. (Found: C, 50.14; H, 3.80; N, 5.90; S, 13.32. C₁₀H₉O₄NS requires C, 50.20; H, 3.76; N, 5.85; S, 13.38%).

2-Phenylimino-3-phenyl-5-phenylazo-4-thiazolidone was prepared by the method of Bhargava and Goswami (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 763). Similarly the thiazolidone was condensed with a number of aryl diazonium chlorides. The properties of these compounds and their analytical data are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Diazonium chloride of amines.	Colour in acetic acid.	M.P.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.
Aniline	Dirty yellow	167°	8.65	8.60
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	Pale yellow	170°	8.34	8.29
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	Yellow	157°	8.38	8.29
α -Naphthylamine	Brown	138°	7.52	7.58
β -Naphthylamine	Scarlet-red	143°	7.63	7.58
Sulphanilamide	Bright yellow	153°	14.23	14.19

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